

Enhanced corrosion resistance of next generation martensitic stainless steel for future energy sector

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates cryogenic processing (CP), an alternative green technology, for improving corrosion resistance in energy sector applications, including fusion. CP opens the door to new tailoring options for materials used in extreme conditions by tailoring the microstructure of the materials and, consequently, their final properties, such as corrosion resistance. The resulting microstructural changes were confirmed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atom probe tomography (APT), and additional *in-situ* and *ex-situ* scanning photoelectron microscopy (SPEM) observations tailors microstructural evolution directly after its application, and later during tempering. The corrosion behaviour was tested using potentiodynamic measurements and exposure to different corrosive environments (nitrogen/oxygen atmosphere with high humidity) in scanning Kelvin probe force microscopy (SKPFM) in order to observe the growth of the passive layer and changes in surface potential. Investigating the corrosion properties and microstructural features together clarifies the formation of carbides over intermetallic enrichment zones, which stabilises the microstructure. The development of next-generation metallic materials for current and future energy sectors is facilitated by this pioneering work, which provides important research for the application of CP.

1. Introduction

Research into the ferrous alloys used in current and future energy systems focuses on improving their performance and prolonging their life cycle [1]. This entails optimising materials' performance (toughness, strength, durability), reducing maintenance costs and addressing sustainability goals in energy sectors (particularly related to extreme environments) [2]. There are 5 key priorities in energy sector in regards to future ferrous alloys: (i) performance in harsh environments where improved corrosion resistance at high temperatures, cryogenic

temperatures, in the presence of highly corrosive media or even high-energy particles (in the fusion sector) is required, (ii) optimized manufacturing and maintenance costs, with emphasis on prolonged life-cycle and improved manufacturing of the ferrous alloys, (iii) improved coatings and surface engineering, (iv) development of emerging energy technologies (hydrogen-based technology, carbon capture and utilization, nuclear fusion materials) and (v) sustainably produced net-zero ferrous alloys (with a lower CO₂ footprint, reduced alloying elements, and recyclable and circular properties) [3–6].

More specifically, the challenges in the future fusion sector remain in

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improving alloys (including ferrous and non-ferrous alloys, such as W-alloys) to withstand high temperatures, pressures and energies, as well as strong magnetic fields and helium embrittlement [7–10]. This is particularly important to further de-risk progressive material degradation and failure. High-Cr ferritic/martensitic steels, such as Eurofer97 and F82H, deliver properties for withstanding such extreme conditions, making them ideal materials to construct the first wall of future fusion reactors and next-generation fission reactors. However, investigations of these steels show that the microstructural changes induced by exposure to high temperatures and high energy particles cause alloy segregation, void growth and increased precipitation of secondary phases that form during and after exposure [11–14]. These changes strongly affect the resulting properties of the material, such as corrosion and wear resistance, longevity and maintenance costs in the scope of the application [5].

Literature review showed that these microstructure changes of ferrous alloys are mostly related to the mobility of chromium (Cr) at grain boundaries (GBs), which act as enrichment or depletion zones for alloying elements [15,16]. Furthermore, prior austenitic grain boundaries (PAGBs) also exhibit increased Cr concentrations, which can affect the final properties of the alloys due to grain boundary embrittlement and matrix dealloying. Regarding the precipitation of carbides and carbonitrides, increased precipitation is observed, particularly in relation to the formation of $M_{23}C_6$ carbides [5,17–20]. These carbides are considered highly unstable over long exposure times in extreme settings, such as those of future fusion reactors. Furthermore, these precipitates also display agglomeration and coarsening, which has a negative effect on the final properties, such as mechanical properties, through swelling and embrittlement. Contrary to this, however, an increase in $M_{23}C_6$ carbides is also considered to be favourable for hardening the steel, which can compensate for the swelling effect [15,21]

Regarding corrosion resistance, studies of fusion materials have shown that the presence of Cr in ferrous alloys plays an important role in building up a favourable passive layer. Different corrosion studies of fusion materials have shown that two layers form: an inner layer enriched with chromium oxides and an outer layer enriched with iron oxides. The Cr-oxides that form the passive layer have been identified as the Cr_2O_3 oxide type, while the Fe-oxides have been identified as magnetite (Fe_3O_4), hematite ($\alpha-Fe_2O_3$), and complex and mixed Cr-Fe oxides with other alloying elements. The literature also shows that a higher Cr content may have a detrimental effect on future fusion steels, causing thermal embrittlement related to increased Cr carbides at the grain boundaries that deteriorate corrosion resistance [22]. Questions have been raised about how to deal with these issues, and opportunities have been provided for new ways for the modification/tailoring of the microstructure and corrosion resistance to be found through different techniques or surface processes.

One of the possibilities is cryogenic processing (CP), which is a sustainable, green and cost-effective technology, which exposes materials to subzero temperature, usually around 77 K, for a certain time (usually 24 hrs) and modifies the material properties at both surface and bulk level. CP is sustainable technology, because it prolongs the life-cycle of the material and with this reduces the consumption of new (critical) raw materials per application life-time. It is classified as green technology because it does not emit any greenhouse gases, such as CO_2 or CH_4 , the nitrogen is renewable and the energy for gas liquification can be used from renewable sources. The technology is also cost-effective because, for some applications, no additional heat treatment or coating application is needed. Furthermore, surface and bulk properties, such as mechanical properties, corrosion and wear resistance, are changed at the same time, avoiding long processing times and costs related to complex procedures with multiple processing steps [23,24].

The corrosion behaviour of ferritic/martensitic steels has been studied in relation to the energy sector, including the future fusion sector. However, research into the influence of CP on the corrosion resistance, passivation behaviour and Cr-Fe oxide dynamics of materials

for future fusion applications is still limited. Some studies have been conducted on CP and corrosion resistance, mostly on tool steels. These studies have shown that CP modifies the passive layer development and the layering of oxides that resulted in improved corrosion and tribo-corrosion resistance. In addition, to our knowledge, no study has been conducted where the same energy material was exposed to different soaking times of CP (shorter and longer exposure times) and different types of CP (e.g. multicycling CP) at the same time, in comparison to classical CP (deep cryogenic processing at 77 K for 24 h). This creates other possibilities for reducing costs and making the CP even more sustainable in terms of energy consumption.

This work attempts to address all five challenges in the energy sector. In this study, we aim at improving the performance of an alternative fusion material (EN X17CrNi16–2), which can also be used in other energy sectors for supply and infrastructure. EN X17CrNi16–2 offers certain advantages over existing standard candidate materials (Eurofer97 and F82H) for fusion reactor applications in terms of mechanical strength and corrosion resistance [25–27]. However, its potential limitations in terms of radiation resistance and low-activation performance require more thorough evaluation. Standard low-activation steels, such as reduced-activation ferritic/martensitic steels, are designed to minimise long-term radioactivity under neutron irradiation [28,29]. Furthermore, the radiation tolerance of RAFM steels has been extensively investigated. These have demonstrated relatively stable swelling resistance, acceptable embrittlement behaviour and predictable microstructural evolution under irradiation conditions that are relevant to fusion systems [30,31]. By contrast, the irradiation behaviour of EN X17CrNi16–2 is less well understood, particularly at high neutron fluences, where phase instability, radiation-induced embrittlement and activation issues may be significant. However, EN X17CrNi16–2 contain alloying elements that may lead to higher activation levels. Therefore, more detailed research between EN X17CrNi16–2 and these established materials would clarify its suitability, advantages and limitations in fusion reactor environments. Furthermore, this study addresses the improved manufacturing and development of new energy technology for surface and bulk engineering, such as cryogenic processing (CP). The effect of CP on EN X17CrNi16–2, martensitic stainless steel, is probed by combining various techniques, including *ex-situ* and *in-situ* observations of alloying dynamics and detailed microstructural analysis (scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atom probe tomography (APT), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and scanning photoelectron microscopy (SPEM)). Additionally, testing of corrosion resistance and analysis of passive layer/corrosion product layer (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) and SPEM) is conducted and correlated with the observed microstructural features and alloying elements dynamics. Finally, this study suggests a novel way of reducing CO_2 emissions from the energy sector and the steel and tool industries by using CP, while providing more environmentally friendly techniques for processing various materials. Through CP, this research delivers insight into creating new combinations of microstructure and properties that can deliver improved alloys that present higher stability under extreme conditions.

2. Methods

2.1. Material, processing, microstructure and phase analysis

The proposed cryogenically tailored Cr-rich ferrous alloy was EN X17CrNi16–2 (chemical composition in wt%: 0.16 C, 0.81 Mn, 0.02 S, 0.04 P, 0.30 Si, 0.10 Mo, 1.55 Ni, 15.25 Cr, Fe base other elements below 0.1) from producer ESG Edelmetall-Scheidservice GmbH. The samples were divided into 2 subgroups, the control group is marked as MS-C and the test group is marked as MS-T. The temperature of austenitization was fixed at $T_a = 1300$ K with holding time of 0.5 h and quenching rate (1073–773 K) ~ 10 K / s, afterwards the control subgroup MS-C was subjected to 1 cycle of tempering at 753 K for 2 h, whereas the other test

subgroup MS-T was subjected to CP for 24 h at 77 K followed by 1 cycle of tempering at 753 K for 2 h. To test the effect of shorter exposure to CP on the alloy, a separate sample group with 8-hour CP exposure (denoted as MS-8h) was also produced. To test the multicycling type of CP, where the material is periodically exposed to changes in temperature over a given period, the material was exposed to two 8-hour cycles from RT to 77 K and back to RT (held for 6 h, before next cycle), followed by an immediate one cycle of tempering at 753 K for 2 h (see Fig. 1). These samples are marked as MS-multicycling. For all cases, the cooling and warming rate during CP was identical set at 10 K/s.

All specimens were heat treated in an Ar atmosphere under high vacuum at the Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials (MPI-SusMat), Germany. Ar atmosphere was used to eliminate the influence of N₂ gas on the microstructure during hardening and tempering. Samples were metallographically prepared for further analysis according to Jovičević-Klug et al., 2021 [32] for the preparation of CP ferrous alloys. To evaluate the entire evolution of the microstructure and chemistry, samples were obtained before the application of CP (denoted as MS-BCP) and after the CP (denoted as MS-ACP), as presented in Fig. 1. The final state of the material after individual procedures were also sampled. The microstructural analysis of the EN X17CrNi16–2 ferrous alloy was performed using a Zeiss Crossbeam Merlin I scanning electron microscope (SEM) at MPI SusMat. A Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer with a Cu K α X-ray source was used for quantitative phase analysis. The diffractometer is equipped with micro area optics (500 μ m x 500 μ m beam size), 5-circle goniometer and HyPix3000 area detector. Measurements were performed as a continuous symmetric overview scan with a step size of $\Delta 2\theta = 0.01^\circ$, a count rate of 4°/min and a power setup of 45 kV/200 mA. Rietveld simulation was used to quantify each phase from the measured data.

2.2. Focused ion beam (FIB) / Scanning transmission electron spectroscopy (STEM)

Lamellae for (S)TEM studies were prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB)-SEM dual system (Helios NanoLab 650, FEI, USA) using an in-situ lift-out technique. During lamella preparation, the specimens were protected with a 300 nm thick electron-deposited W capping layer and an additional 2.5 μ m thick ion-deposited W capping layer deposited at the selected ion acceleration voltages/beam currents of 20 kV/1.6 nA and 30 kV/0.7 nA, respectively. The sample was extracted with gallium ions at 30 kV/21 nA. In the next step, the samples were transferred to

the Cu FIB lift-out grids using an OmniProbe 200 micromanipulator, where the final thinning and polishing of the lamella was performed using an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and beam currents of 2.5 nA–80 pA. In the final step, the FIB was operated at 1 kV/100 pA for 1 min on each side of the lamella, removing the amorphous residue and gallium artefacts and achieving the desired thickness of < 20 nm, enabling atomic resolution in STEM. The lamella was also investigated with selected area electron diffraction (SAED) for crystallographic probing of the samples. For SAED analysis, phase identification and crystal orientation, CrysTBox was used [33].

High-resolution STEM experiments were performed with a probe Cs-corrected JEOL ARM 200 CF microscope operating at 200 keV. The probe semi-convergence angle was 24 mrad and the HAADF detection angles were set to 68–185 mrad. For chemical analysis, a JEOL Centurio EDS system with a 100 mm² SDD detector and a Gatan Quantum ER double EELS spectrometer were used.

2.3. Atom probe tomography (APT)

Atom probe tomography (APT) specimens were prepared by two-stage electropolishing of matchstick samples using the universal electrolyte [34]. The specimens were analysed using a Cameca Invivo 6000 operated in laser-pulsed mode, with 300 pJ pulse energy, 200 kHz repetition rate, 50 K base temperature, and 4% target detection rate. Data reconstruction and analysis was performed using AP Suite 6.3. Crystallographic features on the detector were used to determine the field and image compression factors and to spatially-calibrate the reconstruction. Elemental C peaks were observed in C⁺⁺, C⁺, C₃⁺⁺, C₃⁺, and C₄⁺⁺ molecular and charge states [35]. The ¹⁴N⁺⁺ peak at 14 Da could not be distinguished from ²⁸Si⁺⁺, so ⁵²CrN⁺ and ⁵³CrN⁺ peaks at 66 Da and 67 Da were considered representative of the specimen N distribution.

2.4. Thermodynamic modelling

Thermodynamic modelling was conducted in order to understand the phase fraction and evolution during exposure to cryogenic temperatures followed by the tempering. The calculations were performed with Thermo-Calc Software using TCFe11 and MOBFE6 databases.

2.5. In-house X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and scanning photoelectron microscopy (SPEM)

In-house X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed using a Physical Electronics PHI Quantera II spectrometer equipped with an Al-K α source at 1486.6 eV, in Darmstadt, Germany. A pass energy of 112 eV was used to acquire the survey scan spectra; these were acquired with an energy step size of 0.1 eV. Core spectra from XPS studies were peak-fitted using CasaXPS software, version 2.3.22, Teignmouth, UK.

Scanning photoelectron microscopy (SPEM) was performed at the ESCA Microscopy beamline at the Elettra Synchrotron Radiation Centre. For more information on the beamline and technique, see [36,37]. The base pressure of the microscope chamber was 3×10^{-10} mbar and the photon energy was 740 eV. The samples were pre-hardened and then analysed in-situ during CP (24 h) and tempering (823 K for 2 h for both samples) for both setups (control/CP). Prior to the experiments, the samples were ion sputtered with Ar to remove the oxide layer and surface impurities. The cleanliness of each sample was thoroughly checked and no contaminants were found. High spatial resolution and spectral mapping of the surface chemistry of the samples was performed. The surface chemical maps of C 1s, Cr 2p, Fe 3p, Mn 3p and V 2p were recorded at photon energies of 740 eV. A subtraction of the topography signal was also performed to ensure that the photoemission intensity maps represented the correct chemical contrast, using existing procedures [18] for correct interpretation of the maps. Data analysis was performed using IgorPro9, WaveMetrics (Portland, OR, USA) and Origin,

Fig. 1. The figure shows the different heat processing types of the EN X17CrNi16–2 alloy, including all three CP types.

version 2022, OriginLab Corporation (Northampton, MA, USA). Furthermore, a 30% NaCl solution was used in the mobile glow box setup to investigate the oxidation build-up on the pristine surface of the CP sample prepared under vacuum and inert atmosphere conditions and analysed in SPEM.

2.6. Electrochemical testing

Potentiodynamic polarization measurements were carried out using a Vertex One potentiostat from Ivium technologies on metallurgically prepared samples according to Jovičević-Klug et al. [38]. The sample was placed in an electrochemical cell, where an area of 0.2829 cm² was exposed to the electrolyte using an O-ring of diameter 6 mm. The sample in contact with 30 wt% NaCl aqueous aerated solution at environment with ambient conditions (21 °C and 50% relative humidity) was stabilized for 30 mins to obtain the open circuit potential and the potentiodynamic polarization was carried out from -0.500 mV vs OCP to 400 mV vs OCP at a scan rate of 1 mV/s, and the values were later converted and reported against Ag/AgCl reference electrode potential. For each testing group made at least three measurements in order to assess the reproducibility of the electrochemical data. However, only the best-performing results were selected to represent the data, which follow the average trend of each group.

The solution volume used was 25 mL. The selection of 30 wt% NaCl was made to create a more aggressive corrosion environment and accelerate corrosion and align this study with our previous work on Eurofer97 steel, which is already considered for fusion applications. The idea was to expose the materials to a more aggressive ionic environment to simulate the use of salts in future fusion reactors and to indicate the development of pitting, passivation stability and possible crevice corrosion susceptibility more quickly [18,39–42].

2.7. Scanning Kelvin probe force microscopy (SKPFM) measurements

SKPFM measurements were carried out using an Asylum Research Cypher ES Environmental AFM with environmental control capability (temperature, humidity). During the measurements, a two-pass raster scan was performed at each line: topography was recorded in the first pass, and the contact potential difference was recorded in the second (nap) pass. During the second pass, the tip is lifted to a predefined height to measure the surface potential. Conductive Ti-Ir-coated Si tips (ASYELEC.01-R2) procured from Oxford Instruments were used to carry out in situ SKPFM measurements during oxide build-up. Relative humidity (RH) was maintained at > 90% RH by purging the cell with humidified nitrogen (first 24 hrs) and then oxygen (last 24 hrs) flowing through an external humidification setup. Surface potential maps were obtained at a scan rate of 0.5 Hz to track the changes occurring on the surface. Each frame of the potential map took ~30 min to capture. The output potential signal obtained from the SKPFM must be inverted to determine the actual Volta potential differences of sample vs. tip [43]. All Volta differences reported here are obtained by reversing the polarity of the values.

2.8. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

A FT-IR spectrometer from Bruker Optik GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany, model VERTEX 70 v connected to an external sample analysis chamber and one external detector chamber was employed for the infrared measurements. The sample was inserted in a manipulator adjustable in horizontal and vertical axes and also in angle. Dry argon atmosphere was used to flush the analysis chamber at a rate of 40 l/h. The employed detector was a Liquid Nitrogen cooled HgCdTe detector that was previously cooled down for at least one hour before the spectra acquisition. The spectrometer was equipped with a mid-infrared source, a KBr beamsplitter and was configured with 2 mm aperture and 4 cm⁻¹ resolution. The infrared data were acquired by 1024 scans repeated ten

times and this procedure was carried out for sample and for the background (fresh polished sample without corrosion). The setup employed in this study is schematically presented in Fig. 2.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermodynamics modelling and in-depth microstructure analysis with APT and TEM

Thermodynamic modelling (Fig. 3a) predicted that at sub-zero temperatures M₂₃C₆ carbides (both Fe-rich and Cr-rich types) precipitate/form in conjunction with Ni-rich FCC phase in a BCT martensitic matrix that also develops a Cr-rich subversion type, due to high Cr concentration of the alloy. Furthermore, the high Cr content also induces precipitation of the intermetallic σ -phase, which is expected from around 600 K to 800 K. The transformation towards the FCC phase (related to austenite, retained austenite (RA) and reverted austenite (REA)) is expected from 980 K onwards. Further analysis with XRD, APT and (S)TEM was conducted in order to compare and correlate modelling results with actual experimental results. The quantitative XRD results (Fig. 3b and Table 1) show the phase ratios of the different samples, as well as the phase evolution path at all stages of heat treatment. The major phase evolution variation was connected to the FCC austenite phase in the form of RA in the martensite matrix. In the control sample (MS-C), the presence of austenite was 17.8 vol%, compared to 0.5 vol% in 24-hour CP sample (MS-T), 0.8 vol% in MS-8h, and 0.7 vol% in MS-multicycling sample. These results indicate that CP regardless of the type and duration of application can successfully minimise the presence of RA. However, the most successful rate is attributed to MS-T due to the longest CP exposure time of 24 hrs (↓97% reduction of RA) followed by CP-multicycling (↓96%) and CP-8 hrs (↓95.5%). This falls in line with the cumulative effect of CP exposure time on the reduction of RA with CP [1]. The next difference lies in the ratio of precipitates and carbides within the matrix. Three main carbide phases were identified (M₂₃C₆, M₇C₃ and M₂C₃) for all samples, wherein compared to thermodynamic modelling only one type was identified. Overall, increased precipitation of carbides was observed in all CP groups, particularly in the carbide type of M₂₃C₆ (CP-24h ↑20%, CP-8h ↑32% and CP-multicycling ↑8%). This is related to the increased precipitation of two types of M₂₃C₆ (M=Cr, Fe) and Cr-rich M₂₃C₆ carbides (Cr₂₃C₆), which correlate well with the theoretical modelling. Regarding the other two carbide types (M₇C₃ (M=Cr, Fe, Mo) and M₃C₂ (M=Cr, Fe, Mo)), the precipitation trends are less clear. For the MS-T group (CP 24 hrs), a slight increase of roughly ↑8% and ↑3% was observed for both groups, accordingly. Whereas for groups MS-8h and MS-multicycling the decrease of precipitations for both carbide types was observed (MS-8h ↓4% and ↓7%; MS-multicycling no change for M₇C₃ and ↓14% for M₃C₂). This indicates that the slight variations are the result of the different local chemistry of the samples and probed volume. The lack of modelling results compared to experimental results for these two types of carbides is due to kinetic limitations [44] and limited modelling of prior state, as the M₇C₃ and M₂C₃ are majorly related to the prior processing history of the alloy that is not fully removed by the austenitization [19,20], that diverges from the complete solution-based state modelled through thermodynamic calculations. Additionally, the limited insight provided by the modelling is related to missing or inaccurate data [45], lack of micro segregation/chemical heterogeneity [46] and overall simplified models [47]. Furthermore, the XRD results (Fig. 3b) showed clear phase development in each group. The most notable difference is in the MS-C, where a clear peak for FCC (austenite) can be observed, as well as the successful transformation of FCC into BCT directly after CP (MS-ACP).

Another observation was made in correlation to the evolution route of the selected EN X17CrNi16-2 alloy. The results show that, prior to tempering or CP treatment, the volume percentage of austenite was 5.8% (see the results for samples MS-BCP in Table 1), while the volume percentages of M₂₃C₆, M₇C₃ and M₃C₂ were 1.3%, 1.6% and 1.7%,

Fig. 2. Schematic of the FT-IR instrumentation employed in the current study, showing the infrared beam pathway from the spectrometer until the external detector.

Fig. 3. a) Thermochemical modelling results of phase formation from 77 K to 1300 K for EN X17CrNi16–2. b) XRD results of all six groups for the region of FCC and BCT to show the shifts and different phase development.

Table 1

phase composition of all six samples: MS-C (the control sample with no CP); MS-T (the main test sample with 24-hour CP); MS-BCP (the sample after hardening and before CP with no tempering); MS-ACP (the sample after hardening with 24-hour CP and no tempering); MS-8h (the sample with an 8-hour exposure to CP); MS-multicycling (the sample with a multicycling CP type involving an 8-hour exposure at 77 K, followed by 6 h at room temperature, and a further 8-hour exposure at 77 K).

Group	FCC	BCC/BCT	M ₂₃ C ₆	M ₇ C ₃	M ₃ C ₂
MS-C	17.8	74.1	2.5	2.6	3
MS-T	0.5	90.6	3	2.8	3.1
MS-8h	0.8	90.6	3.3	2.5	2.8
MS-multicycling	0.7	91.4	2.7	2.6	2.6
MS-BCP	5.8	89.6	1.3	1.6	1.7
MS-ACP	1	94.7	1	1.8	1.5

respectively. Whereas the presence of RA, M₂₃C₆, M₇C₃ and M₃C₂ was around 1 vol% directly after CP (24 h), it was 1.8 vol%, 1 vol%, 1.5 vol% and 1 vol%, respectively. Directly after CP, the highest volume percentage of martensite was detected compared to all the other treated groups (see Table 1, sample MS-ACP, ↑28% compared to MS-C and ↑8%

compared to MS-BCP). From this can be postulated that the source of the increased precipitation carbides (especially the M₂₃C₆ type) after CP is the M₇C₃ carbides and the first generation of M₂₃C₆ carbides formed during the hardening process. Additionally, it is postulated that the presence of Cr-enriched M₂₃C₆ after CP can be directly correlated to the migration of free Cr atoms to nearby defects during CP. These defects then nucleate new M₂₃C₆ nanoscopic carbides during subsequent tempering (see TEM and APT results). Similar mechanism observations were made for high-alloyed ferrous and energy steels by Jovičević-Klug et al. [5,19,20,48].

Further results by SEM and supporting results such as electron diffraction energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), inverse pole figure (IPF) and kernel average misorientation (KAM) provided further insight not only into the precipitation dynamics, but also into changes related to the matrix for selected samples (for MS-C and MS-T see Fig. 4a-j, for other two CP groups see Supplementary Material 1 & 2). The IPF results for MS-C sample showed no preferable orientation of the grains compared to the MS-T sample, where the orientation changed after CP to the preferred orientation of {101}. This is highlighted by the clear difference between Fig. 4b and 4g as well as by the pole figures presented in

Fig. 4. a,h represent scanning electron microscopy images of investigated areas, b and i are the, inverse pole figure (IPF) maps, c and j are the energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) composite maps, d and k are the phase maps obtained with electron backscatter diffraction (ESBD), e and l are the mapping of the Kernel average misorientation (KAM) for both selected main groups (MS-C and MS-T with 24 h CP, respectively). F and m present the pole figure presentation of the texture development of the BCT/BCC phases and g and n are the IPF projection of the orientation for the ϵ -martensite. Parts a-g are for control sample MS-C, whereas h-n for test sample MS-T with 24 h CP.

Fig. 4 f and m. EDS results (Fig. 4c & h) of both samples showed that the matrix is homogeneously alloyed with Fe and Cr, whereas in individual carbides Mo is found. The Mo-rich carbides based on the local chemistry and morphology are associated to the M_3C_2 carbide forms, whereas the much smaller and more homogeneously distributed ones are predominantly associated to the M_7C_3 and $M_{23}C_6$ carbides. EBSD results for both samples indicated the presence of 3 main non-carbide phases, FCC (austenite), BCT (martensite) and HCP (ϵ -martensite) (Fig. 4d & i).

Correlative EBSD results confirmed the observations made by XRD data regarding the FCC phase. The results were as follows: control MS-C, 17.3 vol%; MS-T, 0.5 vol%; MS-8h, 1.0 vol%; and MS-multicycling, 0.8 vol%.

The carbides are, due to their relatively small size not separable from the FCC and HCP phases, thus a chemical-based separation (EDS mapping) was performed for the IPF to validate the orientation and phase association to specific regions of the samples. The results, indicate

clearly that MS-C displays higher amount of FCC, which is predominantly related to the presence of REA. The pole figures and IPFs confirm that the majority of the austenite is related to the REA form and not to the RA one, since the individual austenite patches have not a uniform orientation within a single prior austenite grain (see large patches in Fig. 4b that show similar orientation of the martensite laths). Furthermore, the austenite patches deliver a consistent orientation relationship of the $\langle 110 \rangle$ to the neighbouring martensite laths $\langle 111 \rangle$ that follows the Kurdjumov–Sachs orientation relationship for REA [49]. In contrast, the MS-T sample displays no clear visual presence of FCC (see Fig. 4i), which supports the XRD results and expectation that CP averts the formation of REA. Instead, a higher fraction (increase up to 50%, i.e. from 2.3% to 3.5%) of ϵ -martensite is formed in the MS-T versus the MS-C sample. This in turn modifies the orientation distribution related to both α -martensite and of ϵ -martensite. The pole figures of the α -martensite (Fig. 4m) in the MS-T sample display a strong grouping of the orientations into a 3-fold rotation, which follows well the austenite to α -martensite transformation. However, for the MS-C sample, this is not formed owing to the transformation of the α -martensite to REA. The retransformation also delivers a secondary martensitic evolution that creates a separate generation of α -martensite that in turn creates a larger spreading of the orientation, as seen from Fig. 4f. This in turn also induces changes to the orientation distribution of the ϵ -martensite (see Fig. 4g), at which the MS-T displays a much clear texturing and lower spreading (see Fig. 4n) than the MS-C, despite the higher fraction of ϵ -martensite for the MS-T sample over the MS-C one. Similar texture and phase characteristics were also determined for the MS-8h and MS-multicycling samples as can be seen from Supplementary Material 1 & 2. However, the texture changes are less pronounced for these two samples compared to MS. Particularly, MS-multicycling sample shows a closer texture relation to MS-T (see Supplementary Material 2). This can be explained by the shorter exposure time to the CP for these two samples over MS-T, which is further supported by the correlation between the total exposure time and texture development as can be seen from the comparison of Supplementary Material 1 a & 2 a with Fig. 4b and i.

The overall resulting changes in microstructure, phase distribution and their orientations also lead to changes in the distortion of the matrix. As seen from the KAM plots in Fig. 4e and l, the FCC phase and its immediate surrounding retains a high level of distortion in the MS-C sample owing to the retransformation of the phases and the incorporation of the local stress fields resulting from the rigidity of the surrounding α -martensite. In contrast, the MS-T sample shows a more homogeneous and higher degree of misorientation throughout the microstructure, indicating a potentially higher straining of the lattice. Interestingly, for both samples, regions of nearly no misorientation are found (see blue-coloured regions in Fig. 4e and l), with these regions appearing with higher frequency in the MS-C sample. These regions are related to the prior austenite that during the austenitization developed grains with low carbon content and higher Cr content. These grains are thus larger than the martensitic ones as well as show low KAM values due to minimal lattice distortion, thus being close to ferrite [50]. However, CP seems to also enable further modification of these grains by postulated increased mobility of the alloying elements that in turn induce further transformation towards finer martensite. Since, the direct transformation from ferrite to martensite is not possible, even with tempering, the proposed CAR mechanism, firstly observed by Jovičević-Klug et al. [51], can explain this behaviour. In this specific case, the ferrite-like martensite is proposed to be destabilized by the lattice expansion and changes in the alloying elements mobility with CP. Upon heating with tempering, the martensite transforms to REA, but then with longer tempering the austenite retransforms into a tertiary martensite. Since the transformation is directly towards REA, the formation of the intermediate ϵ -martensite is not necessarily induced, thus creating fine martensitic patches with purely α -martensite structures. However, as the alloying is lower, the mechanism can result in a heterogenous formation

resulting in intermediate fine and large martensite grains/laths formation. This is visually confirmed by the phase identification with EBSD, presented in Fig. 4i, where also the individual larger patches of martensite laths show limited or even no presence of ϵ -martensite. Instead, this retransformation should lead to characteristic enrichments of boundaries with Cr that also act as new nucleation sites for carbides, predominantly of Cr_{23}C_6 type that create the characteristic thick carbide rim. This mechanism will be further discussed with TEM and APT analysis of the samples.

The carbide growth and formation is however implied not only on the grain boundaries of the MS-T sample, but also within the grains. As presented in Fig. 5a and b, the sample displays clear formation of needle precipitates, which are distributed primarily in the larger martensitic patches. The precipitates show a clear crystallographic relation to the parent martensitic grains, displaying a 3-fold symmetry indicated by their orientation of their long axis, which are usually more characteristic in heat resistant steels over prolonged service at high temperatures [52]. An example of this is provided in the insert of Fig. 5b, which show the clear needle morphology that with their arrangement looks similar to CP-induced precipitates found in specific aluminium alloys [53]. Additionally, the precipitates also form in the Cr-rich residual δ -ferrite that also presents a core-shell development due to the competing Cr-diffusion between the precipitates and the carbides at the boundaries (see Fig. 5c). Local chemical probing of the largest found needle precipitates (see Fig. 5d), presented in Fig. 5e, indicates that the needle precipitates are N-rich compared to the carbides at the boundaries. The EDS local chemical probing also shows that the precipitates are less Cr-rich, however, this can be also attributed to the size effect. The precipitates are confirmed to be exclusively in highly-ordered needle form that are observed as spherical precipitates, as presented in Fig. 5f, when the orientation of the martensite laths is in the $\langle 110 \rangle$ directions. This confirms the priorly implied crystallographic relation to the martensite laths, which is confirmed through EBSD. The IPF mapping, presented in Fig. 5g, discloses that the precipitates have a core-shell structure, which on the outside display a predominantly colinear relation to the martensite, while the inside shows a 90° rotation to the martensite structure. The phase analysis confirms that the core is of hexagonal structure, which fits well with the Fe_3C model structure, while the shell was identified to be potentially at first as Cr_7C_3 , but the confidence index was lower than 0.1. Resultingly, a high-resolution EBSD scan with longer integration time was performed on the region with precipitates to confirm the correctness of the identified phases. The resulting phase analysis, presented in Fig. 5i, changes the interpretation of the shell to Cr_{23}C_6 model structure with an average confidence index of 0.15. The results also follow the prior crystallographic relation of the core and shell of the needle precipitates to the martensitic lath that indicates a cube-on-cube orientation relation of the shell and a 90° rotation of the core.

In contrast the MS-C sample presents no clear formation of needle-like precipitates. The majority of the carbides are formed at the grain boundaries and only seldom presence of precipitates in the martensite laths is identified with SEM, as seen from Supplementary Material 3 a. Interestingly, the precipitates do not present a needle form and instead show a more randomized form (see Supplementary Material 3 b-c). Additionally, the size of the precipitates in the MS-C follows well with the precipitate cores of the needle precipitates in MS-T, but have no clear relation to the localized Cr enrichment (see Supplementary Material 3 d-e). This indicates that the needle-shaped shell is a result of a separate, subsequent precipitation mechanism that seems to be exclusively related to the application of CP. This is also further confirmed with the additional imaging, EBSD and chemical mapping of the δ -ferrite phase (Supplementary Material 3 f and 4), that again do not display any precipitation in the inner part of the grains, even despite the considerably higher alloying with Cr within them and at the grain boundaries (see table in Supplementary Material 4). The chemical mapping also clearly depicts that the δ -ferrite phase shows a clear Cr-rich and Ni-depleted

Fig. 5. a-d are different BSE images that present the microstructure of the MS-T sample and presence of elongated precipitates. e presents the composite elemental map of image d, indicating the chemical difference between the needle precipitates and carbides situated at grain boundaries. Fig. f displays the perceived round shape of the precipitates in MS-T sample under specific crystallographic orientation of the martensite laths. g and h are the resulting IPF and phase distribution maps of the region marked in a, respectively. A higher resolution EBSD phase mapping of the region of needle precipitates, marked in h, is presented in figure i.

chemical state that is typical for δ -ferrite in Cr-rich steels [54]. To confirm the crystallographic relations and the individual phases of both MS-C and MS-T samples, high-resolution TEM and SAED analysis was performed. The TEM results (Fig. 6a-f) with both dark field (DF) and high angle angular DF (HAADF) accompanied by EDS probing confirm the results from SEM and EBSD. The MS-C sample displays no clear fine needle precipitates (Fig. 6a) and a lower distortion of the lattice, due to the higher relaxation of the stress in the vicinity and within the REA grains (Fig. 6b). The REA grains are clearly visualized by the slight depletion with Fe as seen from Fig. 6c. In contrast, the MS-T sample displays nanoscopic precipitates in specific regions and martensitic laths (example in Fig. 6d). The martensite presents high degree of distortion and formation of high density of dislocations visualized by the high contrast in the HAADF image in Fig. 6e. The nanoscopic precipitates within the laths can be visualized additionally through the slight enrichment with Cr as presented in Fig. 6f. The local SAED analysis for the MS-C sample confirms that the majority of the phases is related to the Cr_7C_3 and M_{23}C_6 carbides and martensite (example provided in Fig. 6g). The thicker grain boundaries that display rounded carbides (further examples in Supplementary Material 6 a-d) in both MS-C and MS-T are

associated with the core-shell formation of the M_3C_2 carbides that are encased in the M_7C_3 and M_{23}C_6 carbides shell as presented in Fig. 6h. The SAED also confirms that the ϵ -martensite has a strong divergent crystal structure from the matrix α -martensite, which follows the proposed step-wise transformation through REA. The M_3C carbides are identified with SAED probing of a larger region of the MS-T, presented in Fig. 6i. The SAED clearly shows (see marking in Fig. 6i) that the multiple precipitates have a correlation with both the matrix martensite and austenite by the previously discussed transformation mechanism that follows the cube-on-cube and Kurdjumov–Sachs orientation relationship. Surprisingly, these transformations are located predominantly along highly distorted regions that do not show a clear correlation with Cr-enrichment (see Supplementary Material 6 g-h) compared to the few precipitates in MS-C (see Supplementary Material e-f). This again confirms that the increased precipitation and their needle shape is related to the changed stress state of the material that also enables the higher mobility of the alloying elements (particularly C and Cr). To elucidate the dynamics of the alloying elements, we employed APT analysis of the selected samples.

Fig. 7 shows reconstructed Fe, Cr, Cn (consisting of C, C3 and C4),

Fig. 6. represents the (S)TEM data obtained for two main samples (MS-C a-c, MS-T d-f), in order to confirm the matrix phase composition and carbide types. The yellow arrows in d and e mark the nanoscopic carbides forming in the MS-T sample. Parts g-i are representative TEM sample areas of MS-C (g) and MS-T (h-i) for which the local SAED were made to confirm phase types in both samples. Note that the SAED for image i was taken from the entire image area.

CrN and P positions, for (a) the MS-C specimen and (b) a MS-T specimen, as determined by APT. The MS-C specimen contained grains of retained austenite and martensite, whereas the MS-T specimens contained only martensite. The martensite grains contained nanoscale plate-shaped carbides, indicated in Fig. 7a-b with dotted boxes. Both reconstructed volumes have been oriented to view some of these carbides in-plane.

The compositional variation was measured between the austenite-martensite interface, and selected element profiles are shown in Fig. 7c. There is slightly higher Fe content in the martensite (80.3 ± 0.3 at%) than the austenite (79.0 ± 0.2 at%) but approximately equal Cr, Ni and Mn content in each grain. The austenite holds higher C (1.8 ± 0.1 at%), N (0.19 ± 0.01 at%) and P (0.04 ± 0.01 at%) than the martensite (C 0.7 ± 0.1 at%, N 0.08 ± 0.01 at%, P 0.05 ± 0.01 at%). Other elements show no significant variation across this interface. Composition profiles were also calculated through the short axes of the plate-shape carbides and significant inter-precipitate variation was observed. Selected composition profiles are shown in Fig. 7d-e, where faint lines indicate the profiles from individual carbides, and solid lines indicate the average profile. The plate-shape carbides in the MS-T specimen are more strongly alloyed with Cr, C, Mn and N, with the C, Mn and N content in the MS-T carbides approximately double that of the MS-C carbides. P content appears slightly lower in the MS-T specimen, but low counts prevent confident quantitative conclusions. With the peak C content reaching only ~ 2.0 - 4.0 at% it is likely that trajectory aberrations are significantly affecting compositional accuracy for these

very small, high-field carbides, and the real C content is likely much higher. Still, these results support the hypothesis that the CP promotes diffusion of solute elements, which precipitate into more strongly-alloyed carbides upon tempering. The effect is most pronounced for the carbide-forming elements: C, Cr, Mn, and potentially N.

In a different MS-T specimen to that shown in Fig. 7b, a larger carbide was captured at the edge of the reconstructed field-of-view with different geometry and composition. Fig. 7f shows reconstructed Fe, Cr and Cn positions, and overlapping iso-concentration surfaces (iso-surfaces, iso.) of C at 4 at% and Cr at 26 at%. The bulk composition in the core of the carbide is Fe 65.3 ± 0.2 at%, Cr 17.6 ± 0.1 at%, C 14.5 ± 0.1 at%, and all others summed 2.7 ± 0.2 at%, suggesting this is a $M_{23}C_6$ -type carbide. Interestingly, Cr is concentrated at the edge of the precipitate, which suggests that the Cr mobility is direct towards the carbides. This is indicated with the pink Cr isosurface in Fig. 7f, and the four composition profiles shown in Fig. 7g-j. Each composition profile passes through a different region of the precipitate, with the ROIs indicated in Fig. 7f. Since the carbide is not shown to be related to any clear grain boundary, it can be presumed that the carbide is part of one of the needle-shaped carbides. This is supported by the chemistry with Cr enrichment as well as by the size range that matches with SEM results (see Fig. 5b).

The SPEM technique was used in order to observe further details related to the chemical bonding of the alloying elements with the Fe matrix with the application of CP in comparison to conventional

Fig. 7. Atom probe tomography characterisation of the nanostructures in this alloy. (a,b) Reconstructed positions of Fe, Cr, C_n (consisting of C, C^3 and C^4), CrN, and P ions for (a) the MS-C specimen and (b) one of the MS-T specimens. Dotted boxes indicate regions of interest (ROIs) over carbides which were studied with compositional profiles. (c) shows the composition profile over the austenite (Aus.) and martensite (Mart.) grain boundary (GB) in the MS-C data, and (d) and (e) show composition profiles over the ROIs shown in (a) and (b). (f) Reconstructed Fe, Cr, C_n positions and isosurfaces (iso) of C at 4 at% (red) and Cr at 26 at% (pink) showing an $M_{23}C_6$ carbide in a different MS-T specimen. Dashed and dotted areas in the isosurface view indicate ROIs used for the composition profiles shown in (g–j).

treatment (MS-T vs. MS-C). Furthermore, the chemical dynamics of the selected alloying elements (C, Cr, Fe, Mn and O) and their roles in the formation of precipitates and in the building of the passive layer were traced and analysed. The latter plays an important role in corrosion and surface resistance. The ex-situ observations (Fig. 8) showed the presence of finer precipitates $M_{23}C_6$ for both groups MS-C and MS-T. On the MS-C sample, two points (point 1-marked red and point 2-marked black) were selected for point analysis of different spectra ($C 1s$, $Cr 2p$, $O 1s$ and $Fe 3p+Mn 2p+Cr 3p$) (Fig. 8a). Fig. 8b shows a comparison of these two points in regards to $C 1s$, where point 1 clearly indicates the presence of precipitates (M_7C_3) after tempering, as final state, which corresponds to binding state of C in the form of M_7C_3 carbide [48,55]. To confirm the presence of carbide precipitates, $Cr 2p$ evaluation (Fig. 8c) was also carried out, revealing the characteristic $Cr 2p_{3/2}$ peak, which was shifted in point 1 more to the metallic state [56], confirming the Cr-carbide state. Both $C 1s$ and $Cr 2p$ spectra show the clear difference to the matrix (point 2). More detailed observations of point 2 additionally confirmed the XPS mapping results (Fig. 8d), which show enrichment of matrix with Cr content. Spectra of $Cr 2p$ and $Fe 3p+Mn 2p+Cr 3p$ confirm that matrix is enriched with Cr and Fe (Fig. 8e). This comparison clearly shows that Mn is not an active alloying element in the formation of the M_7C_3 carbides. Additional $O 1s$ measurements confirmed that the binding state at point 1 (carbide) shows different types of metal oxides than at point 2 (Fig. 8 f). In-situ SPEM observations of MS-T before and

after CP revealed important dynamics of alloying elements influenced by CP (Fig. 8g–m).

The single-point spectra obtained after CP also confirm the increased formation of precipitates in the nanoscale range. The $C 1s$ spectrum (Fig. 8g) shows a clear shift to the right (~ 0.2 eV) towards a more metallic state, which is correlated with carbide formation ($M_{23}C_6$) [57, 58]. The same selected position also showed that before (Fig. 8h), there was a depletion of Cr, which is associated with the matrix of the material, and an increase in Cr presence was subsequently observed. This increase is associated with the formation of nanoprecipitates and is induced by changes in local chemistry and stresses due to changes in the crystal lattice (FCC to BCC and HCP). CP and CP after enrichment confirm the proposed mechanism of movement of alloying atoms to regions of lower concentrations through accompanying changes in crystal structure, which also segregate atoms to new locations. To confirm this mechanism, additional observations were made of $Fe 3p$, $Mn 2p$ and $Cr 3p$. These confirmed the observations made by $C 1s$ and $Cr 2p$ that, before CP, there was a predominant presence of Fe and some Cr (due to the high alloying content). After CP, a new, increased $Cr 3p$ peak occurs, as well as a $Mn 2p$ peak, which is inconsistent with the observation of the control sample (MS-C). These observations also suggest that Fe and Cr are not the only alloying elements forming new precipitates, but that Mn is also involved, which was not observed for the control sample. SPEM mapping also confirms the agglomeration of Cr

Fig. 8. a-f represents the results of ex- and in-situ SPEM measurements (for MS-T sample) of MS-C and MS-T (g-t). n-t present detailed analysis of the area, which was enriched with Cr and martensitic laths arranged in a hexagonally shaped arrangement (possible indication of higher concentration of ϵ -martensite). The spectra of the following elements were analysed: $C 1s$, $O 1s$, $Cr 2p$ and $Fe 3p+Mn 2p+Cr 3p$.

and Mn atoms in locations presumed to be associated with the formation of the nanoprecipitates. Regarding $O 1 s$, the mapping was performed to exclude the agglomeration of elements with native oxide (Fig. 8j-m).

The next question addressed was in regard to the formation of ϵ -martensite and carbides versus Cr-rich areas in the matrix. For this reason, the region with an increased concentration of Cr was probed after CP. (Fig. 8n-t). Fig. 8n-o shows the locations where measurements were taken for Cr (P0-P3) and the mapping of MS-T after the application of CP, where increased precipitation of Cr nanoparticles occurred. Fig. 8p shows that the concentration of Cr $2p$ is increased in the carbide-binding state (P0, P2 and P3). Additionally, the P2 point confirms that there are regions of the matrix enriched in Cr where HCP martensite can form. The selected point (P0) also confirms the presence of carbides, with the corresponding C $1 s$ point spectra and the Fe $3p+Cr 3p$ (Fig. 8t) point spectra. Firstly, C $1 s$ (Fig. 8 s) is found in the metallic state of the carbides, and the presence of Fe $3p$ is also confirmed. Furthermore, the $O 1 s$ spectrum (Fig. 8r) is more indicative of metallic oxides, which correlates to the observations in relation to the metallic states of Fe and Cr. All of the observations related to phase transformation, chemical and structural results support the mechanism of a separate transformation pathway that is unlocked by the CP, as observed in previous work of Jovičević-Klug et al. [51]. However, the formation of the needle precipitates connected with presence of the residual ferrite phase stipulates a difference in the mechanism, particularly in relation to the retransformation phenomenon. The APT data indicates that the precipitates are not present as nanoscopic features, but have developed in the several 100 s of nm range thus confirming that the formation must be firstly rapid and secondly already shows the presence of Ostwald ripening in the context of traditional precipitation. The APT and TEM, however, disclose also that the precipitation is dominated by the $M_{23}C_6$ phase, which is correlated to the Cr content and alloying of the precipitates, which seems to step from a heterogenous nucleation and growth mechanism on the M_3C carbides. This is supported by previous studies of regularly treated Cr-rich steels that have shown similar growth mechanism with aging, but not with application of CP [59]. Together with the clear texture and crystallographic relationship of the precipitates with the matrix α -martensite, we claim that the CP increases the mobility of alloying elements, particularly C, N and Cr. The increased mobility, supported by detected local enrichments with APT and changes in the binding state of the elements with SPEM, results in the lowering of the nucleation and growth energy of the precipitates. This is also in agreement with the detected enriched plates of carbides between the martensitic grains that provides a clear evidence for the reduced energy landscape for carbide formation and growth. However, the explanation of the elongated features of the precipitates lies also in the preferred growth directions, which are associated with the lowest migration

pathways of the alloying elements. This then in turn can explain the symmetric perspectives of the precipitation regardless of the presence of local defects and is purely a result of heterogeneous nucleation and growth at the surface of the precipitates. This is also confirmed by APT that shows at the edge of the precipitates Cr-enriched boundary that is considerably higher enriched than the enrichments detected at the grain boundaries in both absolute and relative sense. This supports also the proposed mechanism of the destabilization of the REA with CP as the austenite reverse transformation enacts a fine reformation of the martensitic structure as seen from the EBSD mappings, following the CAR mechanism. However, the larger martensite laths (or part of them) that do not undergo the CAR are then subjected to high mobility of the alloying elements that in turn create the characteristic needle precipitates. This is particularly possible as the lack of transformations allow the sustaining of the critical energy landscape that in turn promote nucleation of precipitates at higher temperatures. As a result, this is also induced onto the residual δ -ferrite that also then surprisingly follow the same precipitation pattern as in the martensite. The entire described mechanism for the CP materials is presented in Fig. 9. This altogether stipulates that CP promotes strong hardening mechanisms through precipitation of carbides and refined microstructure that also results in the stabilization and lock-in of the alloying elements. This in turn is an important aspect that can positively impact also the corrosion resistance of the material with CP. This will be further elucidated with corrosion experiments and probing in the next sections.

3.2. Evaluation of corrosion resistance with in-situ observation of passive (corrosion product) layer

The results of potentiodynamic polarisation measurements in 30% NaCl are shown in Fig. 10 a. It can be observed that the MS-T sample performs marginally better in the anodic region, compared to the MS-C sample, whereas the MS-T 8 h CP (DCT) and multicycling samples behave much poorer compared to the MS-C sample. The MS-T 24 h sample, however, shows much decreased current densities in the anodic as well as in the cathodic branches of the plot. Owing to the aggressive environment used, it can be observed that the samples display a passivating behaviour only over a narrow window. The MS-T multicycled sample and the MS-T 8 h CP samples can be seen to corrode spontaneously, with narrow passivation regions around current densities of 10^{-4} and 10^{-6} A/cm², respectively. The MS-C and MS-T 24 h samples, on the other hand, tend to passivate, but breakdown soon after initiation of passivation. The MS-T 24 hrs CP sample also displays a secondary passivation behaviour between current densities of 10^{-6} and 10^{-5} A/cm².

The superior corrosion resistance of the MS-T sample (24-hour

Fig. 9. Schematic presentation of the CAR mechanism and proposed microstructural and chemical evolution steps during the tempering stage of the CP.

Fig. 10. Electrochemistry testing of all 4 samples (a) and FT-IR results of the selected 2 samples (b).

cryogenic processing) compared to the MS-C can be attributed to a massive reduction in retained/reverted austenite - dropping from 17.8 vol% to just 0.5 vol%, which eliminates microstructural weak points prone to localized attack. The cryogenic treatment (CP) triggers the CAR mechanism, facilitating the migration of chromium and carbon atoms to nucleate a high density of nanoscopic, needle-like precipitates characterized by an Fe_3C core and a Cr_{23}C_6 shell. This refined precipitation prevents the formation of chromium-depleted zones while increasing lattice distortion and dislocation density, as confirmed by TEM and KAM analysis. Furthermore, SPEM and XPS data reveal that MS-T develops a more resilient and chemically complex corrosion product layer; unlike the standard oxide layer in MS-C, the MS-T surface is enriched with iron/chromium nitrides (Fe_xN) and specialized oxide species (Cr and Mn-rich species) that provide a superior barrier against chloride ion penetration in aggressive saline environments.

The poorer corrosion performance of MS-8h and MS-multicycling relative to both the control (MS-C) and the 24-hour test sample (MS-T) is proposed to be a result of an incomplete microstructural and chemical evolution. While the control sample maintains a specific chemical equilibrium, the shorter cryogenic treatments (CP) disrupt this state without providing enough time for the protective "needle" precipitates to fully grow. Specifically, the detailed characterization proves that these samples show a decrease in established carbide types (M_7C_3 and M_3C_2) without the compensatory 20% increase in beneficial M_{23}C_6 nanoscopic carbides seen in MS-T. This leaves the matrix in a "transitional" state where the initial carbides have begun to destabilize, but the secondary, chromium-rich protective shells have not yet fully formed. Furthermore, the 8-hour and multicycling samples exhibit less pronounced texture development and slightly higher levels of retained austenite (0.8% and 0.7%) compared to MS-T (0.5%). This lack of crystallographic uniformity and the presence of "un-transformed" patches could result in local electrochemical instabilities. Consequently, these samples lack the high-density dislocation network and nitrogen-enriched corrosion product layer found in MS-T, while also losing some of the bulk stability present in MS-C, assumedly resulting in an overall higher vulnerability to chloride-induced attack.

FT-IR spectra were obtained in order to identify potential Fe/Cr oxides and other oxide species (Fig. 10 b) (exposure time of 24 hrs in 30% NaCl). These results are consistent with those obtained using other analytical techniques in this work, such as XPS and SPEM (see Fig. 11). Binding of Fe to Cl oxides was identified as a band around 1700 cm^{-1} . Ammonium salts were present on the surface of the samples at wave numbers of around 958 and 920 cm^{-1} . The chlorates and ammonium compounds were also identified using XPS. Goethite ($\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$) was present at 806 and 648 cm^{-1} , akaganeite ($\beta\text{-FeOOH}$) at 1420 and

660 cm^{-1} , lepidocrocite ($\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$) at 735 cm^{-1} and $\delta\text{-FeOOH}$ at 1118 cm^{-1} [60]. These iron oxide hydroxide compounds have been reported in literature on works using infrared spectroscopy [60,61]. Maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) was identified at 680 cm^{-1} [60,61]. Additionally, the results suggest that $\text{Fe}_2(\text{OH})_3\text{Cl}$ could be present at around 800 cm^{-1} [60,61]. It is suggested that the source of the ammonium salts is the interaction between the surface and liquid nitrogen during CP. It was also demonstrated that an increased concentration of ammonia/ammonium salts in the MS-T sample could effectively enhance corrosion resistance by combining with oxides and hydroxides to create green rust. The ratio and thickness of the different oxides also play a role in corrosion resistance. Similar observation have been reported through other studies [18,62].

In-house XPS data of selected two groups (MS-C and MS-T after 24 hrs in 30% NaCl) showed the difference in passive layer/corrosion product layer development. Results of MS-C (control group) showed the predominant presence of Cr-oxides ($\text{Cr } 2p_{3/2}$) compared to MS-T sample group. Detailed observation of $\text{Cr } 2p_{3/2}$ showed that another difference is in the binding states (compounds). In MS-C (Fig. 11 a) presence of $\text{O } 1s$ silicates ($\sim 533.80\text{ eV}$), metal oxides ($\sim 282.82\text{ eV}$) and chlorates ($\sim 534.14\text{ eV}$) are observed. In contrast, in MS-T sample group (Fig. 11 e) also additionally displays signals of the Fe_3O_4 compound ($\sim 531\text{ eV}$) and nitrates ($\sim 534.8\text{ eV}$), and to other two states: metallic ($\sim 529.43\text{ eV}$) and chlorates ($\sim 534.15\text{ eV}$). For Cr in MS-C sample (Fig. 11 b) 4 different binding states of Cr were observed: Cr metal (574.09 eV), Cr oxide with 2 variations - oxide i (574.95 eV) and oxide ii (579.41 eV) and chloride (CrCl_3 at 577.68 eV). Whereas in MS-T (Fig. 11 f) the following binding states were observed; Cr metal (574.65 eV), Cr nitride ($\sim 574.83\text{ eV}$), chloride (576.61 eV) and one type of the oxide (oxide ii) at 577.53 eV . For $\text{Cl } 2p$ spectrum in MS-C (Fig. 11 c) two binding states were observed: alkaline chloride (NaCl) at 198.55 eV and organic contamination (200.13 eV). With Fig. 11, similar observation of NaCl at 197.34 eV and also presence of Fe/Cr chloride at 198.58 eV was observed for MS-T. In order to correlate the exposure in 30% NaCl, also observation of $\text{Na } 1s$ was made for both groups. In MS-C (Fig. 11 d), NaCl (salt) was clearly identified (1069.65 eV), which was also observed for the MS-T sample (Fig. 11 j) at 1071.69 eV together with hydroxides (1072.77 eV). In the passive/corrosion product layer of MS-T (Fig. 11 g) the presence of Fe ($\text{Fe } 2p_{3/2}$) was confirmed in binding state: metal (706.77 eV), nitride (707.66 eV), chloride (712.37 eV) and oxide. The oxide portion corresponds to mixed state of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , which due to the peak shape and similar height, indicates potentially a predominant formation of Fe_3O_4 . Furthermore, low concentration of N (Fig. 11 h) was observed in correlation to $\text{N } 1s$ binding state as Fe_xN (397.12 eV), surface/oxidized (400.29 eV) and ammonium (405.42 eV).

Fig. 11. In-house XPS results of selected two samples (MS-C and MS-T). The presented results a-d are for MS-C with no CP, while e-j are related to the MS-T sample. *Ex-situ* SPEM results for MS-T sample are presented k-p.

SPEM *ex-situ* observations (Fig. 11 k-p) of selected MS-T sample showed with point survey spectrum of location D (Fig. 11 k) the presence of Fe, Cl, O, S, Cr, Na and N (very small amount). The selected overlay with *Cl 2p* shows the formation of NaCl crystals over selected area (Fig. 11 l, marked as A point). For detailed analysis two points were selected (points F and G). The single point spectra of both points showed overlapping *Fe 2p* spectra, which confirms the presence of Fe in oxide and nitride form (Fig. 11 m). Both points show a slight shift in O 1s spectrum, while for point G more nitrate state was detected compared to point F (Fig. 11 n). In addition, observation of C 1s also confirms the presence of more oxides state (Fig. 11 o). The *Cr 2p* spectra of both points showed the presence of Cr oxides, whereas at which point G also showed metallic state of Cr (Fig. 11 p).

The role of the different microstructure on the electrochemical surface reactivity can be visualized by SKPFM measurements when switching between nitrogen and oxygen atmospheres. The extent of

change in potentials when switching from nitrogen to oxygen indicates activity vs. oxygen reduction [63] (Fig. 12). It can be observed from the potential maps in oxygen atmosphere of the MS-C sample (Fig. 12 f-h) and the MS-T sample (Fig. 12 n-p) that the change in potentials occurs across particles larger in size in the MS-C sample compared to the MS-T sample. The difference in reactivity of the particles in the MS-T compared to MS-C is driven by a shift from "bulk" to "tiny" reactive phases. In the control sample (MS-C), chromium is segregated in relatively large, rounded, and randomized carbides - primarily at the grain boundaries, which creates localized regions of chromium depletion in the surrounding matrix and encourages the formation of galvanic cells. Conversely, the 24-hour cryogenic treatment in MS-T promotes the migration of free chromium and nitrogen atoms toward lattice defects, resulting in a high density of nanoscopic, needle-like precipitates with a unique core-shell structure (Fe_3C core with a Cr_{23}C_6 shell). These tiny, finely dispersed particles prevent large-scale chemical heterogeneity

Fig. 12. SKPFM results of both samples a-h for MS-C and i-p for MS-T, where c-e and k-m are in nitrogen atmosphere and 95% RH. f-h and n-p are in oxygen atmosphere and 95% RH.

and are proposed to act as distributed particles that facilitate a more uniform and resilient passive/corrosion product layer. Additionally supported by the near-total elimination of retained austenite and the formation of Cr and Fe nitrides, these nanoscopic features allow MS-T to maintain a stable, protective surface even in aggressive chloride environments where the bulkier, localized phases of MS-C would typically corrode.

4. Conclusions and outlook

This work investigates the effect of cryogenic processing (CP) on microstructural changes that modify the corrosion resistance and surface potential of EN X17CrNi16-2 for use in the energy sector, including the future fusion sector. The conclusions are:

1. Thermodynamic modelling and experimental validation demonstrated that cryogenic processing of this high-chromium martensitic

- steel effectively suppresses retained austenite and encourages $M_{23}C_6$ carbide precipitation. The most pronounced phase stabilisation and carbide evolution is achieved with longer CP exposure.
- SEM-EDS-EBSD analyses revealed that CP suppresses reverted austenite and alters the texture and orientation of martensite (promoting the formation of $\{101\}$ α -martensite and increasing the amount of ε -martensite). It also modifies the distribution of carbides and increases lattice misorientation. The strongest and most homogeneous microstructural and textural evolution occurs in the sample that has undergone the longest CP (sample MS-T).
 - CP uniquely induces the formation of intragranular, crystallographically aligned, needle-shaped core-shell carbides within martensite. This process is driven by CP-enhanced stress and the mobility of alloying elements. In contrast, the untreated CP sample shows predominantly only coarse, boundary-localised carbides.
 - SPEM, APT and TEM demonstrated that CP increases the mobility of alloying elements (particularly C, N, Cr and Mn), which drives the formation of Cr-rich $M_{23}C_6$ nanoparticles and the reorganisation of the matrix, strengthening the steel and potentially improving its corrosion resistance.
 - Corrosion testing shows that corrosion resistance is only improved by 24 h of CP, which eliminates retained austenite and forms Cr-rich nanoscopic precipitates and a robust passive/corrosion product layer. Shorter CP treatments leave the microstructure in a transitional state that degrades corrosion performance.
 - Potential surface mapping on the surface shows that, after 24 h of CP, reactivity shifts from coarse, boundary carbides to finely dispersed, nanoscopic, Cr-rich precipitates. This enables a more uniform passive/corrosion product layer to form, resulting in superior corrosion stability compared to the control sample.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patricia Jovičević-Klug: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Levi Tegg:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Matic Jovičević-Klug:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **J. Manoj Prabhakar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Cristiano Kasdorf Giesbrecht:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Zygmunt Miłosz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Saro Birgani:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Matteo Amati:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Bojan Ambrožič:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Goran Dražić:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Luca Gregoratti:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Julie M. Cairney:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Michael Rohwerder:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of Ethics in publishing

Authors have followed the ethical guidelines stated in the Publishing Ethics Policy.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.corsci.2026.114053](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2026.114053).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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